

OPPORTUNITIES AND PROSPECTS OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATION FIELD

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Abstract. *The article presents an analysis of the issue of using information technologies in education, namely the concepts, goals, types and forms, directions and prospects for their use. The study describes the structure of the modern digital educational environment. The possibilities of information educational technologies in the design and implementation of the educational process, aspects of implementation at the current stage of development of education and in response to the challenges of our time are also determined. The authors of the study highlight the educational potential of information technologies*

Method: *the usage of modern information technologies in the education process and their effects to pupils during the lesson.*

Result: *Having knowledge about the usage of technologies to the lesson and to know how teachers organize to the class with the help of technologies.*

Keywords: *information technologies, infocommunication technologies, education, training, educational digital environment.*

Introduction

Modern science is developing at an unimaginable speed, spreading its achievements to all spheres of human activity. General informatization is reflected in the field of education in the form of the introduction, adaptation and dissemination of numerous information technologies at all levels of education, from preschool to university, as well as additional education. Thus, among the global trends in the labor market that determine the education system today are: freelancing, working outside the office or production premises; changing means of communication between employees; changing processes, tools and methods for managing work processes; interaction between man and robot, man and artificial intelligence; increased speed of decision making and data processing technologies; multitasking [1].

Currently, it can be observed that educational organizations are still in a state of overcoming the traditional problems of the industrial paradigm of education [2]. Training is mainly associated with individual work, an individual assessment system, the issuance of ready-made tasks and initial data, the absence of multitasking and a focus on the correct, only possible solution to the problem. Competency-based training, including competencies of the future, cannot be built on educational technologies of the past, which were most effective and appropriate for training specialists in the industrial era of the 20th century. [2] The transition to a new educational model is possible only if the educational system is fully integrated into the digital environment;

Global changes affecting the modern educational system include the following: changes in methods and methods of delivering information and educational content; changing the nature and methods of access to educational content; changing the nature of interaction between subjects of the educational process; educational content. Over the past decades, educational technologies have undergone significant changes, moving from passive to active, from simply using computers for printing to replacing teachers with robots, the introduction of modern information technologies

and the digitalization of information content in general. Information technology in a general sense is interpreted as the process of accumulating, processing, presenting and using information using electronic means [3].

In the field of education, information technologies are studied in the context of the term “information and communication technologies” (abbreviated as ICT), since the teacher transmits information through communication (most often through computer means) with the student or pupil. We believe that the concept of “information technology” in the context of the progressive development of technology is much broader than the concept of “computer technology”, since the computer is not the only means of using information technology: modern students use a variety of gadgets (phones, tablets, etc.) and are included in social networks, which can also be adapted to suit learning purposes [4]. The basic goal of using information technologies in the educational sphere is to improve the quality of education and create effective motivation for students in the educational process. Using information technology, a teacher can clearly and clearly present educational information, create conditions for students to independently search for and obtain information, and monitor knowledge using computer testing - the potential of such technologies is enormous and depends on the teacher himself [5].

The use of modern digital and information technologies in education will improve the role of the teacher and student in the learning process. The student becomes a more active participant in the educational process, manages it to a certain extent, sets goals for himself (for example, searching for information), learns to operate with a large amount of diverse information, transform it, and gets the opportunity to model processes. The position of the teacher becomes not so much passive as helping, accompanying, supervising [6]. Taken together, the use of information technology in education makes the learning process more effective.

The infrastructure of the modern educational digital environment consists of the following components: web applications and the Internet; hardware and software; mobile applications; Big Data; Learning Management System; modern ICT tools; information visualization technologies, etc. Let's consider the possibilities of information educational technologies in the design and implementation of the educational process: [7]

- blended learning. Depending on the degree of implementation of ICT tools in the educational process, 6 models are distinguished: face-to-face driver, rotation, flex, online lab, self-blend, online driver (as practice shows, all models are used in the Russian education system);[8]

- project-based learning: involves the complete immersion of the student in the educational process when completing a project using ICT tools and information platforms (Defined Learning (formerly Defined STEM));[9]

- mental maps (mindmapping): a technology for visualizing a large amount of information in the form of diagrams, drawings, and keywords. The following free applications are usually used to create mental maps: XMind, Freemind, BubblUs, WiseMapping;[10]

- “end-to-end” immersive technologies (technologies of augmented -AR and virtual -VR reality): designed to facilitate the perception and visualization of abstract concepts, increase the motivation of students when studying complex disciplines, form initial skills when performing logical tasks or physical actions, facilitate learning in an inclusive educational environment (Google Expeditions Kit; Near Sighted VR Augmented Aid; CanonMreal);

- digital tools (Miro; Kahoot; Mentimeter; Zoom; Google Meet, etc.): aimed at organizing distance interactive learning [11].

Thus, the introduction of information technologies into the educational process contributes to the formation of a fundamentally new form of lifelong education, the fundamental basis of which is the self-analysis of the student's self-educational activities, supported by modern ICT tools. That is, information technologies make the education process continuous - the student studies not only in an educational organization, he searches for information, analyzes it, learns about the world, and even builds contact with the teacher and beyond [12].

Conclusion. At the present stage of development of society in general and education in particular, information technology is not an auxiliary tool for coordinating the educational process, but an integral part of the learning process, which has enormous potential. Let us repeat, the potential of information technologies in education can be revealed when the participants in the educational process develop the appropriate competencies (ICT competencies), the teacher's aspirations to make the learning process effective, innovative and, accordingly, apply a creative, non-trivial approach to its organization. Let us note that informatization and digitalization of the education system is a continuous process and an inevitable trend in the development of modern education, and therefore the teacher must follow the path of acceptance and mastery of information technology, and not opposition or rejection. At the present stage of development of education, information technology is one of the basic (and not auxiliary) methods and forms of learning that have great educational and educational potential.

REFERENCES

1. Iriskulov A. T. va boshqalar Kids English pupils book 2-sinf-Toshkent O'zbekiston; 2014.
2. Khodjayev, K. K. (2021). The specificity and complexity of the process of learning English. *International Journal on Orange Technologies*, 3(6), 21-24.
3. Aksal, F. A. (2009). Action plan on communication practices: Roles of tutors at EMU Distance Education Institute to overcome social barriers in constructing knowledge. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 8(2), 33-47.
4. Bialo, E. R., & Sivin-Kachala, J. (1996). The effectiveness of technology in schools: A summary of recent research. *School Library Media Quarterly*, 25(1), 51-57.
5. Blachowicz, C., Bates, A., Berne, J., Bridgman, T., Chaney, J., & Perney, J. (2009). Technology and at-risk young readers and their classrooms. *Reading Psychology*, 30(5), 387-411. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/02702710902733576>.
6. Carlson, S., & Firpo, J. (2001). Integrating computers into teaching: Findings from a 3-year program in 20 developing countries.
7. In L. R Vandervert, L. V. Shavinina, & R. A. Cornell (Eds.), *Cyber education: The future of distance learning*. Larchmont, NY: Mary Ann Liebert, Inc, 85-114. Choi,
8. C. C., & Ho, H. (2002). Exploring new literacies in online peer-learning environments. *Reading Online*, 6(1). Retrieved September 10, 2012, from readingonline.org/newliteracies/lit_index.asp?HREF=choi/index.html Considine,
9. D., Horton, J., & Moorman, G. (2009). Teaching and reading the millennial generation through media literacy. *Journal of Adolescent and Adult Literacy*, 52(6), 471-481.
10. Fidaoui, D., Bahous, R., & Bacha, N. N. (2010). CALL in Lebanese elementary ESL writing classrooms. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 23(2), 151-168. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09588221003666248> Floyd, R. G., Keith, T. Z., Taub, G. E., & McGrew, K. S. (2007).